

SCIANCE

D8.2

**RAISE Secretariat
Terms of Reference**

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Abstract

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The Terms of Reference for the RAISE Secretariat pilot, hosted by the European Science Foundation, outlines the scope, roles, responsibilities and processes governing Secretariat activities in the context of the SCIANCE Coordination and Support Action. The Secretariat provides support to AI in Science Working Groups, coordination, communication and stakeholder engagement. The Terms of Reference also describes sustainability and exploitation pilots aimed at preparing a long-term RAISE structure, providing governance and operational scenarios to ensure continuity of SCIANCE outputs beyond the project duration.

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Terminology / Acronyms

AISWG	AI in Science Working Group
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
RAISE	Resource for AI Science in Europe

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1 Scope of the RAISE Secretariat

The Secretariat Terms of Reference establish the operational framework for the Resource for AI Science in Europe (RAISE) Secretariat pilot, hosted by the European Science Foundation (ESF) in the context of the SCIANCE Coordination and Support Action. They define the guidelines, roles, responsibilities, processes, and rules governing the day-to-day activities and strategic oversight of the Secretariat during the project lifetime.

The Secretariat pilot acts as the sustainability and coordination pillar of the SCIANCE projects, ensuring the continuity of key project outputs including:

- RAISE Digital Hub, a structured, interactive online platform for project resources and outputs, and community consultation tools.
- RAISE Academy, a capacity-building programme for decision-makers on AI-enabled science and policy alignment.
- AI in Science Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), highlighting community-driven priorities for long-term scientific challenges, cross-domain AI for Science research and innovation and interdisciplinary cooperation.
- AI in Science Roadmap outlines feasible infrastructure upgrade scenarios and phased implementation pathways.

The Secretariat facilitates cooperation and community building within the wider AI in Science ecosystem and explores operational scenarios and potential funding models to support AI-enabled science beyond the project duration.

The RAISE Secretariat pilot operates within the SCIANCE project framework and does not constitute a legal entity, funding body or decision-making authority beyond the mandates defined in the Terms of Reference. Strategic, policy and financial decisions remain with the SCIANCE governance bodies and, where applicable, the European Commission.

2 RAISE Secretariat Activities

Recognising the pilot nature of the RAISE Secretariat, activities are prioritised to ensure alignment with SCIANCE project objectives, deliverables, and long-term sustainability goals. Prioritisation is reviewed regularly with the SCIANCE Management Committee and, where relevant, in consultation with the European Commission.

2.1 Operational and Governance Support

Governance and Coordination

- Organise RAISE pilot meetings, including stakeholder consultations on sustainability and exploitation.
- Prepare agendas, background documents, reports, and minutes, and follow up on agreed actions.
- Support preparation of strategic and operational documents related to the RAISE pilot.
- Liaise with the European Commission and RAISE stakeholders, and report on RAISE pilot activities and projects.
- Explore operational interfaces with funding organisations and European infrastructures and initiatives.

Cooperation within the AI in Science Ecosystem

- Facilitate cooperation, communication and community building within the AI in Science Ecosystem.
- Coordinate interfaces and strategic alignment between RAISE pilot activities and projects.
- Act as a contact point for RAISE AI in Science activities with relevant European and international initiatives, infrastructures, networks, and scientific communities.

Monitoring and Reporting

- Monitor the implementation of RAISE Secretariat activities against SCIANCE objectives.
- Maintain a risk register covering operational or financial risks affecting the sustainability of RAISE pilot activities

2.2 Communication, Outreach and Stakeholder Engagement

- Ensure alignment of the communication activities across RAISE pilot projects with the SCIANCE dissemination, communication and engagement strategy and European Commission guidelines.
- Contribute to AIS Summits thematic programs in relation to SCIANCE activities and stakeholder engagement, upon agreement with the European Commission.
- Structure stakeholder engagement in the RAISE pilot through the preparation and management of non-binding Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) with relevant European initiatives, networks, and organisations.

3 Financial and Administrative Support

Financial and administrative support for the RAISE Secretariat pilot is provided by the SCIANCE project.

- Manage financial and administrative tasks related to the RAISE pilot.
- Archive documentation and reporting required for project audits and reviews.

No autonomous budgetary authority is exercised beyond the SCIANCE grant during the pilot phase.

4 Sustainability and Exploitation Pilots

The main objective of the RAISE Secretariat pilot is to prepare the ground for the long-term RAISE structure.

- Contribute to the Sustainability and Exploitation Plan for RAISE deliverable of the SCIANCE project.
- Pilot selected Secretariat functions including communication and stakeholder engagement.
- Explore and document potential governance and hosting models for a long-term RAISE structure, including roles of stakeholders, decision-making mechanisms, and relations with relevant European initiatives.
- Analyse potential funding and operational models, including participation fees for AIS Summits, annual contributions from funding organisations or stakeholders, or hybrid project and membership-based funding models.

5 Hosting Arrangements and Resources

5.1 Hosting by ESF

ESF provides institutional hosting of the Secretariat pilot, including office infrastructure, IT support, and administrative services in line with its established practices.

5.2 Staffing

The Secretariat activities are carried out by the ESF as part of the SCIANCE project, so staffing levels and task allocation reflect project resources and deliverables. Additional expertise may be mobilised through consultancy contracts or short-term support from ESF staff, subject to project rules and budget availability.

5.3 Knowledge and Assets Management

The Secretariat ensures operational knowledge, documentation, and processes developed for the RAISE pilot activities are systematically documented in an internal knowledge register, ensuring transparency, traceability, and sustainability.

At the end of the SCIANCE project, transferable assets (e.g., branding materials, documentation, digital tools) will be placed under secure custodianship with the host of the RAISE Secretariat, pending a decision by the European Commission on the future governance structure of RAISE. Non-transferable assets, including third-party components and jointly owned materials, will be safeguarded through a stewardship framework that ensures continued access and maintenance for RAISE. Should the European Commission establish or designate a legal entity for RAISE, transferable assets will be assigned to that entity. If no such entity is established, the European Commission will determine the appropriate long-term stewardship arrangement.

6 Ethics and Code of Conduct

ESF has established a Charter for Responsible Conduct for its activities. This Charter establishes the ethical and behavioural standards expected of all participants in its activities, including the RAISE Secretariat, from internal staff to external collaborators. It promotes core principles including integrity, transparency, common interest, and sustainability, ensuring that every engagement is conducted in a respectful, inclusive, and professional manner. By fostering a safe environment, preventing misconduct, and supporting ethical decision-making, the Code also ensures legal compliance and accountability, thereby enhancing trust and upholding the reputation of ESF within the scientific community and beyond. This code of conduct only applies on activities where external actors (not ESF staff) are involved. It complements ESF internal Code of Conduct that applies to all ESF staff.

7 Review and Assessment

The scope of the RAISE Secretariat pilot will be periodically reviewed with the European Commission and may evolve depending on developments around the RAISE initiative and support requirements.

Secretariat activities are reviewed through SCIANCE periodic reporting and project reviews. Lessons learned from the RAISE Secretariat pilot and findings from the SCIANCE project will inform recommendations on governance, operational capacity, and sustainability for a long-term RAISE structure.